

**AVERSIVE BIAS IN JUROR DECISION-MAKING:
INFLUENCES OF DEFENDANT RACE AND
MENTAL ILLNESS DIAGNOSIS**

A Thesis By

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Abstract:

Extensive research has documented racial disparities in the U.S. criminal justice system, with Black and Latino defendants facing harsher judgments due to pervasive stereotypes linking race to criminality. Similarly, defendants with mental illnesses face significant stigma in legal settings, especially in cases involving the insanity defense. Despite these established biases, few studies have examined how race and mental illness intersect to influence juror decision-making. The present study examined how the interplay between defendant race and mental illness diagnosis influenced juror verdicts, sentencing, culpability assessments, and a number of trait measures. This interplay was investigated through the lens of aversive racism, which posits that individuals who explicitly endorse egalitarian values may still exhibit discriminatory behavior when their actions can be justified by non-racial factors, such as mental illness. In a mock juror study, using a 3 (defendant race: Black, Latino, White) × 3 (mental illness diagnosis: depression, schizophrenia, none) between-subjects design, 293 undergraduate students participated as mock jurors after reading a randomly assigned murder trial transcript. Results partially supported the hypotheses: predominantly Latinx mock jurors rated Black and White defendants with depression as more guilty, more blameworthy, and colder than Latino defendants or those diagnosed with schizophrenia. Verdict outcomes revealed that depression was perceived as a more “controllable” disorder, leading to harsher judgments of these defendants overall. These findings highlight the complex and subtle ways in which racial and mental illness biases interact to shape juror perceptions, with implications for understanding aversive racism and stigma in legal decision-making.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Social injustice has a long history in psychology and law literature, specifically with regards to juror decision making. Beginning at the time of the Civil Rights Movement and the Civil Rights Act of 1964, focus on Black persons' interaction with the U.S. legal system has been empirically examined in juror decision making research (Espinoza, 2010). In addition to race influencing juror decisions, aspects of gender, attractiveness, socioeconomic status, age, and mental illness have all been shown to impact how jurors decide cases (Mazella & Feingold, 1994; Sommers & Ellsworth, 2009). Defendant mental illness, in particular, has garnered a great deal of recent attention due to the ineffectiveness of the insanity plea, as well as other biasing effects of defendant mental illness diagnosis on juror decisions. However, little research has examined the interactive effects of defendant race/ethnicity, and specific mental illness diagnosis on juror decisions. The little research focusing on these factors has shown mixed results and, as a result, there does not seem to be a clear, theoretical explanation for this bias. Some research on juror bias, when extra-legal factors such as race/ethnicity, and socioeconomic status (SES) are salient, has examined the theory of *aversive racism*, or *aversive bias*, as a possible theoretical explanation for juror decision-making bias (Minero & Espinoza, 2016; Phan et al., 2022). But would aversive bias best explain juror decisions when the combined effects of defendant race/ethnicity and defendant mental illness diagnosis are made salient? The purpose of this study is to examine if the extra-legal factors of defendant race and mental illness diagnosis interact to affect juror bias and if the theory of aversive racism can best explain this bias.

U.S. Institutional Bias Against Blacks

Inequalities against Black individuals in the United States have deep historical roots that are still present today, particularly in education, healthcare, employment, and the criminal justice system. Systemic racism, stemming from slavery and segregation, have continued to reinforce structural challenges that Black communities struggle to overcome. Understanding these inequalities is crucial to

addressing the systems that continue to perpetuate them. According to the U.S. Department of the Treasury, mass incarceration, educational disparities, and healthcare discrimination contribute to the cycle of poverty and limited opportunities for non-White Americans (Bowdler & Harris, 2022; Harris & Feldmeyer, 2009). Negative stereotypes targeting Black Americans have also continued to reinforce the systemic oppression of people of color (Melson-Silimon et al., 2024). The recognition of systemic factors informs which group holds the power to create the cultural narratives and reinforce the racial biases that members of society hold (Lei et al., 2023).

The construction of Black stereotypes originates from the Antebellum Period, in which slave owners characterized Black men as “intellectually inferior” and “beastly” to dehumanize them and argue for their enslavement (Melson-Silimon et al., 2024). In the Jim Crow era, White society often portrayed Black men as “sexual predators” who preyed upon White women, justifying the actions of the Ku Klux Klan in restoring the racial hierarchy (Franklin, 1979). In modern day, the perception that Black Americans are lazy was reestablished with the introduction of the welfare queen trope—a derogatory label which described Black women as calculating, lazy, and having children in order to receive government assistance (Foster, 2017). During Ronald Regan’s presidency and the “War on Drugs”, another racial stereotype that dominated American culture was the association of Black men and drug crimes (Mastro, 2015; Mastro & Stern, 2003). Sensationalized stories about the violent crimes committed by Black criminals in urban communities incited fear in Americans and justified the mass incarceration of people of color. Due to the overrepresentation of Black people in the justice system for drug-related charges, Black Americans continue to be stereotyped as drug dealers and criminals. These pervasive negative beliefs contribute to the broader societal perception of Black Americans as inherently dangerous, shaping public attitudes and influencing policies that disproportionately impact their communities (Mastro, 2015; Skinner et al., 2020). Despite efforts to dismantle these harmful narratives, media portrayals and political rhetoric continue to fuel negative perceptions, making it difficult to overcome the historical prejudices that have long defined attitudes toward Black Americans.

Disparities in healthcare, shaped by prejudice and stereotyping, continue to affect people of color. Black and Latinx individuals face higher rates of child abuse, childhood obesity, lead exposure, discrimination-related stress, and chronic illness compared to White Americans (Harris & Feldmeyer, 2009). Previous studies on racial distrust and perceptions of healthcare providers suggest that Black patients are more distrustful of the healthcare system, and that physicians, in turn, describe them as less educated, more likely to abuse drugs, and lacking social support (van Ryn & Burke, 2000). Minority patients are also less likely to receive empathy from their physicians, adequate information on their medical concerns, or opportunities to be involved in medical decisions (Ferguson & Candib, 2002). In a similar vein, employment and advancement issues have also shown a historical bias against Blacks. Dovidio and Gaertner (2004) found that, in simulated selection decisions, ambiguously qualified Black candidates were recommended less often than White candidates, revealing that bias emerges most prominently when qualifications are unclear. The results indicated that when an applicant was White, participants responded to ambiguous qualifications more as if these qualifications were strong than as if they were weak. However, when an applicant was Black, ambiguous qualifications were perceived as weaker than ambiguously qualified White candidates.

The aforementioned research has demonstrated significant discriminatory practices against Blacks in the institutions of healthcare and employment. Unfortunately, little research has focused on how healthcare for Black individuals involved in the U.S. legal system are treated for mental illness. The following section will examine bias and discrimination against Latinx individuals.

Negative Attitudes Towards Latinx/Hispanics

In 1980, the population of Latinx individuals was 7% of the total U.S. population with about 14.8 million Latinx individuals living in the United States. Now, approximately 62.5 million Latinx individuals reside in America, representing 19% of the total U.S. population (Moslimani & Bustamante, 2023). The rapid growth of the Latinx population is reshaping the nation's cultural and economic

landscape, making it one of the fastest-growing demographic groups in the country. Yet, despite this expanding presence, Latinx persons continue to face significant challenges, including negative stereotypes, poverty, educational inequalities, and discrimination that limit their opportunities for success. While 56% of all Latinx individuals have had some high school education, over a third of Latinx students still do not complete high school (League of United Latin American Citizens, 2024; Moslimani & Bustamante, 2023). According to the U.S. Department of Education, many Latinx students, either by arrests or referrals to law enforcement agencies, fall victim to the school-to-prison pipeline, a dysfunctional system in which harsh disciplinary policies and inadequate support in underfunded schools often lead students to drop out and end up enmeshed within the criminal justice system (League of United Latin American Citizens, 2024). Racial bias and defaulting to law enforcement as discipline exacerbate this problem, disproportionately affecting Black and Latinx individuals. Just as the “welfare queen” stereotype has long misrepresented Black women, media portrayals of Latinx individuals often rely on harmful stereotypes—depicting them as criminal immigrants or burdens on the economy due to perceived overreliance on welfare or large families (Foster, 2017; Reny & Manzano, 2016). These inaccurate narratives fuel public perception that views immigrants as threats to job security and national safety.

The bulk of research tied to the Latinx community, and the legal system is conjoined with immigrant status (Espinoza, 2010). The combined aspects of Latinx immigrants and crime have produced mixed results but overall suggests that Latinx immigrants have little to no impact on crime and violence at a community level (Harris & Feldmeyer, 2009). Harris and Feldmeyer (2009) examined crime rates among ethnic groups in both traditional and non-traditional immigrant destinations—areas like rural regions, New England, and the Midwest that are less accustomed to large influxes of foreign-born, and linguistically isolated immigrant populations. These non-traditional areas are important to study, as public disapproval in such regions can reinforce negative stereotypes, deepen polarization, and influence policies that may restrict the integration of immigrant communities. Using race-disaggregated

violent crime arrest data from California, New York, Texas, and the 2000 U.S. Census, the study found that in traditional destinations, recent Latinx immigration was negatively associated with Latinx violence and unrelated to Black or White violence (Harris & Feldmeyer, 2009). In contrast, non-traditional destinations showed a weak positive link between recent Latinx immigration and both Black and Latinx violence. One explanation for the increases in violence in non-traditional destinations is increased competition between Black and Latinx populations for low-skill labor market positions in areas with limited resources and support for immigrants. New immigrants have less assistance in finding stable employment, financial assistance, and affordable housing. This lack of support may lead to social strain and heightened conflict which generates crime and weakens community cohesion. So, when considering bias toward Latinx individuals in the U.S. legal system and juror decision-making research, we must also take into consideration how a Latinx individuals' legal status, and/or citizenry contribute to juror perception.

Finally, the “War on Drugs,” which disproportionately targeted Black men, has also reinforced the association between drug trafficking and gang violence stereotypes with Latinx males, or Latinos (Demuth & Steffensmeier, 2004). Research suggests that Latinos are frequently portrayed as lazy, dangerous, and a threat to the economy (Foster, 2017; Reny & Manzano, 2016). Like Black individuals, Latino defendants—who often harbor distrust toward the criminal justice system—may be less likely to cooperate during legal proceedings. This perceived lack of cooperation can, in turn, be misinterpreted as guilt or dangerousness, further contributing to biased outcomes.

Race/Ethnicity and Bias in the U.S. Legal System

Historically, minority groups have not been treated equally in the criminal justice system. Black and Latinx individuals are disproportionately affected by blatant racism, racial profiling, stereotyping associated with criminality, and socioeconomic disadvantages (Espinoza, 2010). A recent analysis of police stops across the United States indicated that police officers have been accused of persistent racial bias, especially when it pertains to search decisions and arrests (National Conference

of State Legislatures, 2022). It was determined that the rate of Black people getting stopped declined significantly after sunset, when the race of the individual driving was harder to determine. According to a 2021 report by The Sentencing Project, Black Americans were incarcerated 5 times more than White Americans and Latinx individuals were convicted 1.3 times more than non-Latinx Whites (National Conference of State Legislatures, 2022; Nellis, 2021). Black Americans are more likely to be arrested, convicted, and sentenced to longer terms compared to their White counterparts (Pearson et al., 2007).

In the U.S. legal system, Black men, more than any other racial group, are disproportionately affected by eyewitness misidentifications—a leading cause of wrongful convictions. Research on this phenomenon indicates that faces with stereotypically Black features are more quickly categorized as “Black” than faces with atypical features and are more likely to be misidentified in facial recognition and police lineups (Knuycky et al., 2014). These identification errors are especially common for individuals with darker skin tones, wider lips, and broader noses—features that align with *stereotypically Black* features and are more associated with the “criminal-Black-man” stereotype (Kleider-Offutt et al., 2017). This perception of criminality not only contributes to mistaken identity, but also, reinforces systemic biases in policing and judicial processes, resulting in unjust outcomes for Black men.

The United States population is projected to be 28.6 percent Latinx by 2060. However, Latinx individuals make up almost 30% of the current incarcerated population, meaning that 1 in 6 Latino men have been incarcerated (League of United Latin American Citizens, 2024). In 2016, Urban Institutes collected public data from jails and prisons across all 50 states to assess the mass incarceration of Latinos. They noticed a disturbing lack of data on the number of Latinos in the criminal justice system. This insufficiency was caused by the system’s lack of differentiation between ethnicities. Many states only categorize people as “Black” or “White” and often mistakenly label their Latino population as “White” (Urban Institutes, 2016). This misclassification inflates the reported number of White people in the

prison system, while concealing the true extent of racial disparities within the justice system, especially for Latinx individuals.

Demuth & Steffensmeier (2004) examined Hispanic-Black-White differences in sentences imposed on drug or property offenders in state felony courts. In this research, the authors noted the lack of reliable measures of ethnicity due to Hispanics being classified into either White or Black categories. They hypothesized that Hispanics would receive harsher treatment in the justice system, compared to Whites, since they share many of the same social disadvantages and problems with cultural and media negative stereotypes that Blacks do. Demuth & Steffensmeier (2004) collected data by the State Court Processing Statistics (SCPS) program of the Bureau of Justice Statistics (BJS) for the years 1990, 1992, 1994, and 1996 and examined two dependent variables: incarceration decisions (probation or jail term) and sentence length decisions (in months). They also isolated ethnicity to determine Hispanic-Black-White differences. The results indicated that Hispanic defendants were sentenced similarly to Black defendants and that both minority groups were sentenced harsher than White defendants. It was also determined that Hispanics were the group most likely to be incarcerated at 82.7%, compared to Blacks at 75.7%. For property and drug crimes, Blacks and Hispanics defendants were significantly more likely to be incarcerated than their White counterparts. Furthermore, it was noted that by combining Hispanic and White defendants into a single racial category, the true Black-White difference in incarceration and sentence-length outcomes was masked.

Perhaps the largest research area with regards to Blacks and Latinos interaction with the U.S. legal system has been conducted by examining juror decision-making bias. How are jurors influenced by race/ethnicity of defendants, as well as victims, in the juror decision-making process?

Two extensive meta-analyses examining socio-cultural influences that may bias juror decisions were conducted by Mazella and Feingold (1994) and Mitchell et al., (2005). Though these meta-analyses were conducted ten years apart, both articles came to similar conclusions regarding extra-legal factors that may contribute to juror bias. In the Mazella and Feingold (1994) article, it was found that gender,

physical attractiveness of defendants, and race/ethnicity of defendants, victims, and jurors can have consequential negative impacts on juror decision making. Mitchell, et al., (2005) focused extensively on defendant race and found minority defendants, Black and Latinx, were found guilty significantly more often than White defendants who committed similar crimes. In addition, minority defendants were found more culpable and sentenced more punitively compared with White defendants.

In addition to race/ethnicity as contributing to juror bias in legal research, mental illness has been extensively examined as a contributory bias in juror decisions. The following section will examine this literature.

Perceptions of Mental Illness in the Courts

Perceptions of mental illness diagnosis and disorders varies widely by culture and nationality. In the United States, there is a stigma of persons with mental illness as being dangerous to themselves and others (Corrigan, et al., 2003). This also, to a certain extent, depends on the type of mental illness diagnosis – depression is seen as a less severe form of mental illness compared with schizophrenia (Corrigan, et al., 2003). In addition, people with mental illness (MI) are overrepresented in the United States criminal justice system. Recent statistics estimate that people with serious mental illnesses, including schizophrenia and other psychotic disorders, are incarcerated roughly two million times a year and that almost two in five people who are incarcerated have a history of mental illness (National Alliance on Mental Health, 2024). Pescosolido et al. (2019) examined trends in the public's perception of MI and violence and support for coerced treatment over a twenty-two-year period using data from three National Stigma Studies. The results indicated that by 2018, over 60% of respondents viewed people with schizophrenia as dangerous and a lower, but significant percentage of the public also perceived people with depression to be dangerous. Despite evidence and previous research debunking the myth that people diagnosed with a mental illness commit dangerous crimes, perceptions of potential violence and support for coerced treatment rose over time (Pescosolido et al., 2019). These findings point to the public's tendency to stereotype those with mental disorders and highlight the pejorative

attitude towards mental health, which can lead to inappropriate treatment and increased criminalization of people with MIs. The negative stigma surrounding mental illness must be examined further to understand how they can affect important decisions in the United States criminal justice system—specifically in jury decision making.

Social media and traditional news outlets are often the primary sources through which the public learns about mental health; however, the nature of these portrayals varies across platforms. While social media can offer personal anecdotes and community-based discussions that help reduce stigma, traditional news and entertainment media have historically depicted mental illness in dramatic and inaccurate ways. Stuart (2006) found that news and entertainment media sensationalize mental illness by emphasizing themes of dangerousness and unpredictability, modeling harmful societal responses to the mentally ill. Stories that overstate rare and tragic events, such as school shootings and psychotic breaks, only fuel the belief that those with serious MIs pose a threat to public safety and must be dealt with harshly in the eyes of the law. These portrayals have serious consequences: individuals living with mental illness may avoid seeking help due to stigma, while also experiencing diminished self-esteem (Stuart, 2006). Additionally, media representations feed into societal fears of “differentness” and exacerbate the connection between mental illness and incarceration (Mossiere & Maeder, 2022).

These distorted media portrayals not only shape public attitudes toward mental illness but also influence how legal defenses involving mental health, such as the insanity plea, are perceived. The insanity defense, also known as the “not guilty by reason of insanity” (NGRI) plea, is often misunderstood and misrepresented as a legal loophole, through which criminals can escape punishment (Silver et al., 1994). In highly publicized trials—such as those of Jeffrey Dahmer, John Hinckley Jr., and Charles Manson—media coverage frequently reinforces these views by portraying defendants who plead insanity as dangerous and unstable individuals responsible for heinous and bizarre crimes (Steadman & Coccozza, 1978). The trial of John Hinckley Jr., in particular, which ended in a NGRI verdict after his attempted assassination of President Ronald Reagan, sparked widespread public

outrage. Many viewed the outcome as a failure of the justice system and saw the insanity defense as a tactic used by the guilty to avoid accountability. As a result, public opinion and juror decision-making may be swayed by skepticism and misinformation rather than by legal standards or psychological evidence. Research consistently shows strong public opposition to the NGRI defense and a prevalent belief that it is highly successful. Many doubt the ability of juries and judges to accurately discern whether defendants are truly sane or not, while also believing the plea is overused, allowing guilty individuals to return to society (Hans, 1986).

Silver et al. (1994) conducted a large-scale longitudinal study across eight states to evaluate the accuracy of public perceptions regarding the use, success rates, and legal outcomes of the insanity plea. Their findings revealed that the public's estimate of the insanity plea rate (37%) significantly exceeded the actual plea rate (0.9%). Similarly, the public significantly overestimated both the likelihood of success (defined as the number of acquittals) and the percentage of individuals who are released immediately after a successful insanity defense (Pasewark & Seidenzahl, 1979; Silver et al., 1994). These results highlight public distortions about the prevalence and consequences of the insanity plea, suggesting a widespread misunderstanding of how rarely it is used and the caution with which it is applied. Perceptions of the frequency and effectiveness of the insanity defense are bound to be influenced by sensationalized media coverage, especially when high-profile cases are constantly making headlines. These cases dramatize rare outcomes, perpetuating the false belief that the insanity plea is a common and easily exploited legal loophole—rather than a rarely employed, legitimate defense with minimal success.

While public misconceptions shape broader attitudes toward the insanity plea, individual juror decision-making in the courtroom is often influenced by more nuanced factors—particularly, perceived severity of a defendant's mental illness. Early research in this area has found the severity of the accused's mental disorder is an important factor when describing those individuals found NGRI (Pantle et al., 1980; Pasewark & Seidenzahl, 1979; Roberts et al., 1987; Rogers et al., 1984; Smith &

Hall, 1982). This research suggests that jurors may respond differently depending on the intensity or type of diagnosis attached to a defendant, showing more leniency toward those with severe mental disorders and adopting greater skepticism toward less apparent or “lesser” conditions like depression. Despite the evidence that the defendant’s present demeanor may not be an accurate depiction of their mental state at the time of the offense, jurors often rely on the behavioral observations in the courtroom to make determinations about the accused’s psychological condition during the crime (Whittemore & Ogloff, 1995).

Such observations can be fallacious in cases where defendants have undergone changes in their treatment—either by being taken off medication, placed on new or stronger prescriptions, or were previously deemed incompetent to stand trial but are now proceeding with the use of forced medication. Whittemore and Ogloff (1995) examined how the disposition of insanity acquittees and the mental state of the defendant at the time of the trial can influence sentencing outcomes. At the time of the study, there was great concern over unfair rulings due to jurors not receiving accurate disposition information on where a defendant will be placed after being found NGRI. In an effort to ensure a defendant is properly punished and confined, jurors often lean towards a guilty verdict, especially when they are unsure of where acquittees go (Slovenko, 1983).

Participants were given trial transcripts to read in which defendants’ mental states at the time of trial (psychotic, neurotic, symptom free) and manipulated disposition instructions (indeterminate, capped, and no disposition instructions) were also included. Findings revealed that participants who believed the defendant was exhibiting psychotic symptoms during the trial were significantly more likely to render a verdict of not criminally responsible on account of mental disorder (NCRMD) than a verdict of guilty, compared to those who believed the defendant appeared symptom free (Whittemore & Ogloff, 1995). Individuals who rendered a guilty verdict also thought the defendant should be detained longer than those who rendered a verdict of NCRMD or not guilty. In addition, participants who perceived a defendant to have a more severe mental illness recommended institutionalization over

incarceration more frequently and for longer durations. These findings suggest that jurors' perceptions of the severity of a defendant's current mental state can influence both verdict decisions and sentencing recommendations, regardless of the defendant's actual mental status at the time of the crime. Reliance on observable courtroom behavior or assumptions about visible symptoms highlights a discrepancy between legal standards of criminal responsibility and perceptions of mental illness. This disconnect raises important concerns about the fairness and accuracy of verdicts in cases involving mental illness, especially when jurors lack clear education and instructions regarding mental illness and post-verdict outcomes.

Mental Illness, Race, and Criminal Proceedings

There has been limited research examining juror bias toward racial and ethnic minority defendants with mental illness in legal proceedings. Instead, most existing studies focus on public perceptions of mental illness, support for rehabilitative efforts, attitudes toward the insanity defense, and the association between mental illness and gun violence, while simultaneously not examining racial differences in these areas (Pescosolido et al., 2019; Swanson et al., 2015). A previous study conducted by Mossiere and Maeder (2022) examined how a defendant's mental illness (MI) diagnosis might influence juror decision-making. Participants acted as mock jurors, reading a robbery case transcript in which the defendant's mental illness diagnosis was varied: no diagnosis, a stereotypically violent category of schizophrenia or substance abuse, and a non-violent category of depression or OCD. Participants' attitudes toward mental illness were measured using the Attitude Toward Persons with Mental Illness Scale (APWMI) before the trial, and a post-trial questionnaire collected verdicts, sentencing recommendations, and confidence levels. The experiment found no significant relationship between attitudes and sentencing type, though unexpectedly, more negative attitudes toward MI were associated with shorter sentences. A follow-up study with a community sample produced similar results, finding no clear link between attitudes, diagnosis, or verdict decisions. While these findings were inconclusive, the study was one of the few that examined mental illness outside the context of the

insanity plea and facilitated discussion about jury bias against MI. Still, there was no examination of racial disparities regarding mental illness diagnosis and interactions within the legal system.

Kaur et al. (2023) examined racial and ethnic disparities in mental health treatment and found that, even though mental health treatment rates have increased since the 2000s, the gaps in treatment between White clients and ethnic minority clients has widened. The authors concluded that there could be two possible explanations for this widening gap. One, was that cultural stigma and stereotypes surrounding mental health may discourage ethnic minority individuals from seeking treatment. And two, mental health providers may lack adequate training in delivering culturally competent care, leading to substandard treatment for minority clients. Plummer et al. (2023) examined intake evaluations of racially diverse arrested suspects at the Middlesex Jail and House of Correction in Billerica, Massachusetts. They found that during initial intake evaluations, Black and Latino arrestees were significantly less likely to acknowledge mental health treatment for mental illness compared to White arrestees. If such disparities exist in standard mental health care of ethnic minority clients, it is likely that these inequities are even more pronounced within the legal system.

White (2016) examined the intersection of juvenile mental health diagnoses and inmate race/ethnicity. The study found that minority juveniles diagnosed with a mental disorder were more likely to be referred to the criminal justice system rather than to mental health intervention services when accused of a crime. Additionally, when accused of similar crimes, Black and Latino juveniles with mental health diagnoses were more likely to receive harsher dispositional recommendations for jail, compared to their White counterparts. This begs the question – does the interaction between defendant race/ethnicity and MI diagnosis contribute to biased legal decision-making and outcomes for minority defendants compared to White defendants? And if so, what theoretical framework can help us understand the mechanisms driving this bias?

Aversive Racism and Juror Decision Making

The nature of prejudice and discrimination in the United States has changed drastically over the past few decades. While overt discrimination has been on the decline, subtle forms of bias are still prevalent, manifesting as implicit attitudes and microaggressions (Espinoza, 2010). These covert beliefs may operate outside an individual's conscious awareness and can be difficult to address because they are not intentional. Subtle racism is now being examined in research, especially in systems with high racial disparities and systemic inequality. One such system that has been under much scrutiny is the United States criminal justice system, in which the nature of discrimination within juror decision making is complex and not fully understood.

Aversive racism refers to a subtle form of bias in which individuals will explicitly endorse egalitarian values but also hold unconscious negative feelings or beliefs about minority group members. Based on the theory of aversive racism, people will explicitly claim they have non-racist and egalitarian attitudes but are still likely to demonstrate discriminatory behavior when situations are ambiguous (Dovidio & Gaertner, 2004). Aversive racism theory has been used to examine the unfair treatment of minorities in the criminal justice system, particularly in juror decision making (Minero & Espinoza, 2016; Phan et al., 2022). It highlights the influence of implicit biases and prejudice on legal decisions, even when institutions and individuals claim to be neutral. Since aversive racism operates at a subconscious level, jurors and judges are likely to mask their underlying bias by attributing unequal rulings to non-racial factors. One example of this is research conducted by Sommers and Ellsworth (2000; 2001) which demonstrated that ambiguous circumstances in legal proceedings, where racially salient issues are not present in trial, White mock jurors are more likely to convict Black defendants (Sommers & Ellsworth, 2000, 2001).

Pearson et al. (2007) studied the bias of White people towards Black defendants in the legal decision-making process and found that hate, based on Sternberg's (2003) duplex model of hate,

mediated punitiveness towards the defendants in different ways. Participants read either an unprovoked or provoked assault perpetrated by a Black assailant on a White victim. The unprovoked attack was added as a manipulation to test the idea that aversive racists would discriminate against Black defendants if a factor that was unrelated to race was included. Participants were asked to complete an emotional response questionnaire that assessed for the three theoretical hate components of the duplex model: passion, negation of intimacy, and devaluation (Sternberg, 2003). The findings suggest these 3 hate components were strong predictors of explicit hate— specifically that passion was the strongest predictor of the sentencing length and devaluation was the strongest predictor of support for the death penalty (Pearson et al., 2007). In contrast, the strongest predictor for those with more implicit biases against Black defendants was devaluing, a more cognitive component used to justify negative responses, which would align with the aversive racism model.

Research on the effect of defendant race on jury decision making has had conflicting results, with some studies finding an out-group bias, while others finding little support for this phenomenon. In some cases, the effects of aversive racism were more aligned with the leniency effect that was noted in research conducted by Bucolo and Cohn (2010). The leniency effect occurs when race is made salient and a strong outgroup favoritism occurs (Gamblin & Kehn, 2021). This phenomenon was identified in previous research looking at race salient opening and closing attorney defense statements. Mock jurors were given criminal assault cases to read, in which the opening and closing arguments were manipulated to include race salient messages. Contrary to their original hypothesis, Gamblin and Kehn (2021) found that White mock jurors were more likely to give White defendants guilty verdicts and rate them to be more violent than Black defendants.

These results can be explained by the theory of aversive racism, in that interracial crimes give mock jurors a chance to display themselves as non-racist and non-prejudiced (Braun & Gollwitzer, 2012). In addition, inducing race salience reduces situational ambiguity, which gives reminders to aversive racists that they must monitor their judgements to fit in with their egalitarian beliefs (Pearson

et al., 2009). In a similar vein, an examination of aversive and modern racism conducted by Reynolds et al. supported the leniency effect noted above (2022). Participants were assigned to read a brief interracial criminal trial summary either with or without a race salient manipulation. The strength of the evidence was also manipulated to help participants reach a decision on verdict (guilt/not guilty). The results concluded that aversive racists were more likely to convict a White defendant than modern racists and had a more punitive attitude towards White defendants (Reynolds et al., 2022). In this study, participants were motivated to appear unprejudiced and would overcorrect their unconscious bias, leading to less guilty verdicts for Black defendants. This effect was referred to as the bend-over-backwards effect in this research (Olson & Fazio, 2004).

A possible explanation for the leniency effect is that previous studies did not examine the different kinds of prejudice people hold (Reynolds et al., 2022). Modern racism is used to describe a group of people who believe that they are not prejudiced because they do not support overt forms of discrimination (Reynolds et al., 2022). This group believes that the system is not at fault for the struggles of Black Americans and that Black people are now getting more than they deserve from institutions, such as affirmative action. Modern racists and aversive racists are similar in that both will discriminate when there is a non-racial justification present (McConahay, 1983). However, modern racists demonstrated higher levels of discrimination, especially in hiring settings. Although aversive racism and modern racism are similar to each other, they are theoretically different and influence jurors to discriminate in distinct patterns. Further research is needed to separate both forms of racism to better understand the conditions under which individuals discriminate in the justice system and to figure out a solution to the overcorrection problem that was noted in the previous studies.

Finally, research by Phan et al., (2022) and Minero and Espinoza (2016) specifically applied the theory of aversive racism to examine juror decision-making bias. In Phan et al.'s study, Asian and White defendants were compared. These defendants committed crimes stereotypically associated with their respective ethnic groups—cybercrime for Asians and embezzlement for Whites. Mock jurors judged the

Asian defendant as significantly more culpable and were more likely to find them guilty when the crime aligned with the racial stereotype. In the Minero and Espinoza (2016) study, immigrant defendants from Canada (White), Mexico (Latino), and Kenya (Black) were examined. The authors did not find significant effects for race/ethnicity/country of origin of the defendant. However, when defendant race/ethnicity was coupled with another perceived non-racial negative variable (low SES), mock jurors demonstrated bias. These jurors found the Black and Latino low SES defendants significantly more culpable and sentenced these defendants more punitively compared with low SES White immigrant defendants

The Current Study

A comprehensive examination of previous studies highlights a gap in the research on the interplay of defendant mental illness and defendant race. Both race and mental illness have been extensively studied independently from each other to explore their effects on juror decision making. However, the intersection of these two variables has been underexplored, limiting the understanding of how jurors may respond when both race and mental health are salient in the courtroom. This lack of research limits our understanding of how these two factors together can influence legal outcomes and whether adding one or the other may exacerbate juror bias.

Aversive racism, as applied to juror decision making, is the idea that subtle or unconscious biases can greatly influence a juror's decision-making process, even more so when race and mental illness play a role in the case. In these cases, while jurors believe themselves to be unbiased, they may still rely on negative racial stereotypes unconsciously. This can result in a slanted perception of minority defendants, particularly Black and Latinx defendants. A mental illness diagnosis may also exacerbate or complicate this perception due to the criminalization of serious MIs, and the stigma people may have towards those with mental disorders (Mossiere & Maeder, 2022). As described above, previous research indicates that jurors tend to perceive Black and Latino defendants in a more negative light than White defendants when race is made salient. There are characteristics of a defendant that

have stereotypically been associated with criminality, such as being Black or Latino, being a man, and being unattractive (Mossiere & Maeder, 2022). Similarly, mental illness can also be classified as a defendant characteristic that invokes implicit and explicit bias for jurors and legal professionals. This is because mental illness has often been stereotypically associated with instability and volatility, creating a clear association between mental illness and criminality that should be examined alongside race. Mental health and race often intersect, and these negative stereotypes can worsen the existing racial disparities in our justice system. Specifically, for Black and Latino defendants who are already unfairly linked to negative assumptions about criminality. Through the lens of aversive racism, we hypothesize that mental illness may be used as a “neutral” reason through which jurors may justify giving harsher sentences to minority defendants. This is because aversive racists want to maintain their non-prejudiced image, but can implicitly, or subconsciously, engage in negative behaviors towards minority group members only when their actions can be justified on the basis of a non-race related factor (Pearson et al., 2007).

The purpose of the current study is to investigate the interactive effects of race of defendant and defendant mental illness diagnosis on jury decision-making. Specifically, this will be a 3 (defendant race: White, Black, or Latino) X 3 (mental illness diagnosis: schizophrenia, depression, or no diagnosis) between-groups design. The four dependent measures will be verdict, sentence, culpability, and trait measures. Based on the theory of aversive racism, it is hypothesized minority defendants diagnosed with a perceived less severe mental illness diagnosis (depression) will be found guilty more often, receive more punitive sentence recommendations, be found more culpable, and rated more negatively on a number of trait measures compared to all other conditions. Based on this previous research, the following hypotheses are proposed.

Hypotheses

Based on previous literature on juror decision-making, and the theory of aversive bias (Dovidio & Gaertner, 2004), it is expected that jurors who share the same race or ethnicity as the defendant will

evaluate in-group members more favorably. In addition, jurors of a different race or ethnicity are more likely to evaluate out-group defendants more punitively (Bradbury & Williams, 2013). In addition, based on previous research regarding perceived mental illness diagnosis severity (Corrigan, et al., 2003), it is hypothesized that defendants diagnosed with depression would be perceived as more responsible for their predicament compared with a more severe diagnosis such as schizophrenia.

Hypothesis #1

Based on previous research using White mock jurors, it was hypothesized that Black defendants with depression, and to a lesser degree, Latino defendants diagnosed with depression would most likely receive a guilty verdict compared to White defendants or defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia. However, given that our participants were primarily Latinx, our adjusted hypotheses address this dynamic by predicting our participant pool may show bias to the Black and White defendants, and not the Latino defendant.

Hypothesis #2

It is also hypothesized that Black defendants with depression, and to a lesser degree, Latino defendants diagnosed with depression will receive lengthier sentences when compared to White defendants or defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia. Again, given that our participants were primarily Latinx, our adjusted hypotheses address this dynamic by predicting our participant pool may demonstrate more punitive sentencing to the Black and White defendants, and not the Latino defendant.

Hypothesis #3

It is also hypothesized that Black defendants with depression, and to a lesser degree, Latino defendants diagnosed with depression will be found more culpable compared to White defendants or defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia. Again, given that our participants were primarily Latinx, our adjusted hypotheses address this dynamic by predicting our participant pool may show the Black and White defendants as more culpable, and not the Latino defendant.

Hypothesis #4

It is also hypothesized that Black defendants with depression, and to a lesser degree, Latino defendants diagnosed with depression will be rated more negatively on a number of trait ratings compared to White defendants or defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia. Again, given that our participants were primarily Latinx, our adjusted hypotheses address this dynamic by predicting our participant pool will rate the Black and White defendants more negatively on a number of trait measures compared with the Latino defendant.

CHAPTER 2

METHOD

Participants

The data being used for this study were previously collected. Because most juror decision-making research examining racial bias has found significant results with primarily White participants, we attempted to focus our analyses using only White mock juror participants. However, at the time of analysis, only data from 48 White participants have been obtained. Overall, we analyzed data from two-hundred and ninety-three mock juror participants from different racial/ethnic backgrounds.

Undergraduate psychology students ($N = 293$) acted as mock jurors and were recruited from California State University of Fullerton's Department of Psychology. Some of the students were required to participate for class credit and some volunteered their time. The eligibility criteria required that students be at least 18 years of age or older to participate in the study. The mean age was 19.6 years of age ($SD = 3.28$) which is considerably younger than the typical juror in the United States criminal court system. Seventy-one percent of participants were female, and the racial/ethnic breakdown of participants was 49% Latinx, 21% Asian, 15% White, 3% Black, and 10% Other or Multi-Ethnic.

Design

A 3 x 3 between-subjects design was used for this study. The two independent variables were defendant mental illness diagnosis (depression, schizophrenia, or no mental illness diagnosis) and defendant race (Black, Latino, or White). The four main dependent measures that were examined were the categorical variables of verdict and sentencing, and the continuous variables of culpability ratings, and trait ascription measures. The categorical variable of verdict measured whether the jurors found the suspect *guilty*, *not guilty*, or *not guilty by reason of insanity (NGBRI)*. If jurors found the defendant guilty, they were asked to recommend a sentence for the defendant. The categorical variable of sentencing measured whether the jurors assigned the defendant *a twenty-year sentence with the possibility of parole*, *life in prison with the possibility of parole after thirty years and time for good*

behavior, or life in prison without the possibility of parole. If jurors found the defendant NGBRI, they were asked to recommend a sentence for the defendant. The categorical variable of sentencing measured whether the jurors assigned the defendant *released under the supervision of the state psychiatrist, placed in a high security mental health hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff, or placed in a high security mental health hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff, where upon release from the hospital, the defendant will serve 20 years in state prison.* The quantitative variable of culpability measured jurors' attitudes regarding the defendant's culpability such as confidence in their verdict, defendant responsibility, etc. The quantitative variable of trait ratings measured how jurors rated the defendant's personal trait ascriptions such as trustworthiness, intelligence, etc. (see Appendix C for trial transcript and dependent measures).

Materials and Procedures

Participants signed up for a time and place to complete the study through California State University's Sona systems website. When the participants arrived to begin the study, they were provided with a consent form (Appendix B) that explained the instructions and process of the study. Participants were run in small groups by the experiment administrator. Participants were informed that they would be acting as jurors in an actual court trial and at the end of the study they would need to decide the outcome of the case. They were informed that the study would be examining juror-decision making.

Once participants provided their consent to participate in the study, they were provided a trial transcript (see Appendix C). Participants were randomly assigned to one of the following nine conditions: a Black defendant with depression, a Black defendant with schizophrenia, a Black defendant with no mental illness diagnosis, a Latino defendant with depression, a Latino defendant with schizophrenia, a Latino defendant with no mental illness diagnosis, a White defendant with depression, a White defendant with schizophrenia, or a White defendant with no mental illness diagnosis. The study provided a description of the crime that took place (Murder), the charges against the defendant (Murder in the First Degree), background information of the defendant, the defendant's plea, as well as

summaries from the defense and prosecution. The participants were also able to view a 2" x 3" head and shoulder picture of the defendant. After participants read through the trial packet, they were then asked to render a verdict, recommend a sentence, rate the defendant on several culpability measures (e.g. How guilty is the defendant? How responsible is the defendant? How confident are you in your decision? etc.) and trait measures (e.g., trustworthiness, competence, attractiveness, etc.) (See Appendix D). They were then asked to complete a juror memory form which was used for manipulation check purposes. Finally, participants were asked to provide various demographic information (see Appendix D). The participants were debriefed at the end of the study and were provided with the name and contact information of the principal investigator in case they had further questions or comments. The participants were then dismissed and thanked for their time.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS

The four dependent measures of interest for the current study were verdict, sentencing, culpability, and trait ratings. To examine the effect of the categorical independent variables of race and mental illness on mock juror decisions for the categorical dependent measure of verdict, a logit chi-square analysis was conducted. If mock jurors found the defendant Guilty, or NGBRI, they were asked to recommend a sentence. Separately, logit chi-square analyses were conducted to examine the effect of the categorical independent variables of defendant race and mental illness on mock juror decisions for the categorical dependent measure of sentencing for mock jurors who found the defendant Guilty, or NGBRI. To explore the effect of the categorical independent variables of race and mental illness on mock juror decisions for the quantitative culpability measures, a MANOVA was conducted. To examine the effect of the categorical independent variables of defendant race and mental illness on mock juror decisions for the quantitative trait ratings, a MANOVA was conducted.

Based on the theory of *aversive racism*, it was expected that no main effects for race would be found with White mock jurors. It was not expected that White participants would demonstrate bias towards Black and Latino defendants based solely on race. However, as previously mentioned, we do not have a large participant pool to examine only White participants (N = 48). Though limited research on Latinx jurors' decision making has been conducted (Espinoza, 2010), we would still expect our primarily Latinx participant pool to demonstrate some form of aversive bias toward the Black and White defendants. Though the author admits this examination will be explorative. Similarly, to hypotheses regarding aversive racism with White jurors, only when race was coupled with non-racial variables that are perceived as negative (mental illness) did we expect jurors to demonstrate bias toward the Black and, possibly, the White defendants. We expect this bias to be especially true for Black and White defendants with depression. Depression is viewed as a less severe mental disorder compared with schizophrenia and patients diagnosed with depression are often perceived as more responsible for their situation compared

with a perceived, more severe diagnosis such as schizophrenia (Foster & O’Mealey, 2022). It is expected that our primarily Latinx mock jurors will find the Black and White defendants diagnosed with depression, guilty more often, sentence these defendants more punitively, find these defendants more culpable, and rate these defendants more negatively on a number of trait measures compared to all other conditions.

Verdict

Based on the theory of aversive racism, Hypothesis One predicted that jurors would be more likely to find Black and White defendants diagnosed with depression guilty significantly more often compared to Latino defendants or those diagnosed with schizophrenia. A logit chi-square analysis was used to examine the relationship between the independent variables of defendant race and mental illness diagnosis, and the dependent measure of verdict (not guilty, not guilty by reason of insanity – NGBRI, or guilty). As hypothesized, results revealed significant differences for verdict based on the combined effects of defendant race and mental illness diagnosis, $X^2(16) = 26.084, p = .05$. Mock jurors (primarily Latinx) gave the more severe sentence of *Guilty* to Black and White defendants diagnosed with depression (see Table 1). In addition, we did find a main effect for mental illness diagnosis for verdict. As hypothesized, those defendants, regardless of race, diagnosed with depression, were found *Guilty* significantly more often than those diagnosed with schizophrenia, $X^2(4) = 14.69, p = .005$ (see Table 2).

Juror Recommended Sentence

The second hypothesis proposed that primarily Latinx mock jurors would sentence Black and White defendants more punitively when diagnosed with depression, compared with Latinx defendants and defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia. A logit chi-square analysis was used to examine the relationship between the independent variables of defendant race and mental illness diagnosis, and the dependent measure of sentencing. If jurors found the defendant NGBRI the sentencing recommendations were as follows: 1. *Released under the supervision of the state psychiatrist*, 2. *Placed in a high security mental health hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff*, 3. *Placed*

in a high security mental health hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff, where upon release from the hospital, the defendant will serve 20 years in state prison. If jurors found the defendant Guilty the sentencing recommendations were as follows: 1. *Twenty-year sentence with the possibility of parole*, 2. *Life in prison with the possibility of parole after thirty years and time for good behavior*, or 3. *Life in prison without the possibility of parole*. Contrary to Hypothesis Two, a logit chi-square analysis did not reveal a significant interaction for sentencing based on the combined effects of defendant race and mental illness diagnosis for those participants who found the defendant NGBRI, $\chi^2(32) = 25.644, p = .779$. Participants who found the defendant Guilty, also did not show a significant interaction for sentencing based on the combined effects of defendant race and mental illness diagnosis, $\chi^2(16) = 9.80, p = .877$. There were no significant main effects for defendant race or defendant mental illness diagnosis for those participants who found the defendant NGBRI or Guilty ($p > .05$).

Defendant Culpability

The third hypothesis predicted primarily Latinx mock jurors would find Black and White defendants more culpable when diagnosed with depression, compared with Latinx defendants and defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia. A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the independent variables of defendant race and mental illness diagnosis, and the dependent measures of culpability (e.g. defendant's responsibility of the crime, defendant's intentionality, belief in defendant, confidence in decision, etc. see Appendix D). Consistent with hypothesis three, there was a significant interaction between defendant race and mental illness diagnosis for culpability, Roy's Largest Root, $F(17, 270) = 3.162, p < .001, \eta^2 = .166$. The individual culpability measures found to be significant were *How guilty was the defendant*, $F(4, 283) = 4.28, p = .002, \eta^2 = .06$; *blame*, $F(4, 283) = 3.48, p = .008, \eta^2 = .05$; and *How did the viciousness of the crime impact your decision?*, $F(4, 283) = 3.15, p = .015, \eta^2 = .04$. Overall, Black and White defendants diagnosed with depression were found more guilty, more blameworthy, and the viciousness of the crime impacted mock jurors' decisions significantly more than all other conditions (see Table 3).

There was also a significant main effect for defendant race and the culpability measures of *how guilty was defendant?*, $F(2, 290) = 6.39, p < .002, \eta^2 = .04$; *responsibility*, $F(2, 290) = 8.82, p < .001, \eta^2 = .06$; *confidence in correct decision*, $F(2, 290) = 11.78, p < .002, \eta^2 = .08$; *believe defendant's version of crime*, $F(2, 290) = 3.98, p = .02, \eta^2 = .03$; and *blame*, $F(2, 290) = 11.69, p < .001, \eta^2 = .08$. Overall, Black and White defendants were found more culpable compared with the Latino defendant (see Table 4).

Finally, a significant main effect for defendant mental illness diagnosis and culpability was also found for the culpability measures of *how guilty was defendant?*, $F(2, 290) = 15.97, p < .001, \eta^2 = .10$; *responsibility*, $F(2, 290) = 16.08, p < .001, \eta^2 = .10$; *confidence in correct decision*, $F(2, 290) = 11.95, p < .001, \eta^2 = .08$; and *blame*, $F(2, 290) = 22.07, p < .001, \eta^2 = .13$. Overall, defendants diagnosed with depression were found more culpable compared with those defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia (see Table 5).

Defendant Trait Ascriptions

The fourth hypothesis stated that primarily Latinx mock jurors would rate the Black and White defendants diagnosed with depression significantly more negatively on a number of trait measures compared with Latino defendants and defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia. A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the independent variables of defendant race and mental illness diagnosis, and the dependent measures of defendant trait ascriptions (e.g. competence, attractiveness, warmth, aggressiveness, trustworthiness, etc.). Consistent with Hypothesis Four, there was a significant interaction between defendant race and mental illness diagnosis, Roy's Largest Root, $F(12, 273) = 3.638, p < .001, \eta^2 = .14$. The individual trait ratings found to be significant were *How ethical is the defendant*, $F(4, 281) = 2.59, p = .04, \eta^2 = .04$; and ratings on *how cold/warm* jurors found the defendant, $F(4, 281) = 2.74, p = .029, \eta^2 = .04$. Overall, Black and White defendants diagnosed with depression were less ethical and rated as colder compared with Latinx defendants and those diagnosed with schizophrenia (see Table 6).

There was also a significant main effect for defendant race and the trait rating measures of *trust*, $F(2, 290) = 4.97, p = .008, \eta^2 = .04$; *ethicalness*, $F(2, 290) = 5.96, p = .003, \eta^2 = .04$; *cold/warm*, $F(2, 290) = 10.58, p < .001, \eta^2 = .06$; and *aggressiveness*, $F(2, 290) = 7.84, p < .001, \eta^2 = .04$. Overall, Black and White defendants were rated significantly more negatively on a number of trait measures compared with the Latino defendant (see Table 7).

Finally, a significant main effect for defendant mental illness diagnosis and the trait rating measures of *trust*, $F(2, 290) = 3.15, p < .05, \eta^2 = .02$; *ethicalness*, $F(2, 290) = 25.37, p < .001, \eta^2 = .15$; *cold/warm*, $F(2, 290) = 28.82, p < .001, \eta^2 = .16$; and *aggressiveness*, $F(2, 290) = 10.46, p < .001, \eta^2 = .07$. Overall, defendants diagnosed with depression were rated significantly more negatively on a number of trait measures compared with defendants diagnosed with schizophrenia (see Table 8).

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION

Interpretation of Findings

The present study examined whether defendant's race (Black, Latino, White) and mental illness diagnosis (depression, schizophrenia, or none) interact to influence juror decision-making. Consistent with previous findings (Mazella & Feingold, 1994; Mitchell et al., 2005), our findings revealed that extra-legal factors substantially shape juror perceptions. However, the patterns of bias do not reflect overt racial discrimination. Instead, the differences in verdict, culpability judgments, and trait ratings suggest the presence of subtle aversive forms of prejudice that tend to emerge in ambiguous situations. These results can be best understood through the lens of aversive racism theory (Dovidio & Gaertner, 2004), which posits that individuals who openly endorse egalitarian values may still display discriminatory behavior when decisions are ambiguous or when non-racial justifications are available — such as a defendant's mental illness diagnosis in the current study. Considering past research on this framework, it was hypothesized that White mock jurors would only demonstrate significant bias toward minority defendants when these defendants were diagnosed with a perceived “less severe” mental illness (Minero & Espinoza, 2016; Sommers & Ellsworth, 2000, 2001). Specifically, we expected Black and Latino defendants with depression to be found guilty more often, receive lengthier sentences, rated as more culpable, and evaluated more negatively on a number of trait measures compared to White defendants and those with schizophrenia.

There is an important caveat to note – this study was originally designed to examine aversive racism among White jurors. However, because our final sample consisted mainly of Latinx participants, the findings instead offer an exploratory look into how racial bias may manifest within a primarily Latinx juror pool. As a result, these findings should be interpreted with caution and considered a preliminary contribution to a largely understudied area. Given that most prior research on racial prejudice in the legal system has found juror racial bias with primarily White participant jurors against

minority defendants, and that we had a limited number of White mock jurors (16%), we adjusted our hypotheses. The bulk of our participants were Latinx (49%), and Asian (21%). Because this data set consisted of primarily minority students, I was unable to examine only White juror responses. The U.S. Bureau of Justice Statistics has historically reported that jury pools tend to be disproportionately composed of White men, and the average age of U.S. trial jurors is approximately 50 years. Additionally, past research has shown that death-qualified juries and jury selection processes disproportionately include older white men (Lynch & Haney, 2011). Thus, we acknowledge that our participant pool does not accurately resemble the demographics of the average U.S. trial jury. Still, based on the theory of aversive racism, we expected our primarily Latinx and Asian participant population would demonstrate bias toward the Black and White defendant, but not the Latino defendant.

Consistent with Hypothesis One, verdict outcomes demonstrated that mock jurors (primarily Latinx) were more likely to give guilty verdicts to Black and White defendants diagnosed with depression, compared with Latino defendants and those diagnosed with schizophrenia. White defendants diagnosed with depression were the group most likely to receive a *Guilty* verdict. There was also a main effect for mental illness diagnosis: regardless of race, defendants with depression, were found *Guilty* significantly more than those diagnosed with schizophrenia. This interaction supports the notion that depression is often perceived as a less severe and more “controllable” mental illness (Foster & O’Mealey, 2022), leading jurors to view these defendants as more responsible for their actions—and therefore, more deserving of punishment. When race was added to the mix, negative stereotypes may have amplified these disparaging perceptions, activating in-group or out-group biases among Latinx participants and leading to more negative attitudes towards White and Black defendants (Espinoza, 2010).

Surprisingly, and contrary to Hypothesis Two, our study did not find a significant interaction or main effects for sentencing recommendations. Although the verdict outcomes indicate bias consistent with aversive racism, sentencing decisions did not differ significantly based on defendant race or mental

illness. One possible explanation for this is that jurors may likely adhere to more consistent sentencing guidelines once a verdict has been reached, applying similar penalties regardless of whether the defendant was found Guilty or Not Guilty by Reason of Insanity (NGBRI). Another interpretation concerns the issue of statistical power. Because our participant numbers were substantially reduced within each condition, particularly after verdict decisions were split between Guilty and NGBRI outcomes, power was significantly compromised, and the resulting small cell sizes may have limited our ability to detect meaningful differences. As a result, we are unable to identify subtle sentencing biases that might otherwise emerge in a larger sample.

The interaction between defendant race and mental illness on the dependent measure of culpability ratings further highlights the subtlety with which aversive bias operates. Consistent with hypothesis three, mock jurors rated Black and White defendants with depression as significantly more guilty, more blameworthy, and more vicious than all other conditions. Both Black and White defendants were perceived as more guilty and more responsible for the crime than Latino defendants, with White defendants rated the most negatively overall. This pattern reflects a significant main effect for defendant race. Although we initially hypothesized no main effect for defendant race based on the theory of aversive racism, these results may be explained by the predominantly Latinx sample pool. As previously discussed, most prior research on juror racial bias has focused on White jurors' evaluations of Black defendants. However, the limited studies examining Latinx jurors suggest that racial bias may manifest differently across cultural contexts. For example, Bradbury and Williams (2013) found that Black defendants were less likely to be convicted by juries with a higher percentage of Black jurors, but more likely to be convicted by juries composed mostly of White and Hispanic jurors. This suggests that out-group bias towards Black defendants may also emerge among Latinx jurors, particularly in ambiguous decision-making contexts. Similarly, Leippe et al. (2023) found that both Black and Hispanic jurors exhibited out-group discrimination in their evaluations, particularly when they perceived the decision as highly important, suggesting that social identity and motivational factors can heighten intergroup bias —

explaining why our predominantly Latinx sample rated Latino defendants more favorably than Black or White defendants.

In addition, jurors also expressed greater confidence in their decisions, were less likely to believe the testimony of Black and White defendants and blamed these defendants more. Similarly mental illness diagnosis influenced perceptions of culpability: defendants with depression were viewed as more guilty, vicious, and blameworthy than those with schizophrenia. These results align with previous literature suggesting that defendants with mood disorders are often perceived as more morally accountable for their actions than those with psychotic disorders (Pescosolido et al., 2019; Whittemore & Ogloff, 1995). In the current study, this perception appears to have been mediated by racial cues, indicating that jurors may have drawn upon stereotypes that associate race and mental illness with criminality when considering a defendant's guilt and culpability. Significantly, Black defendants diagnosed with depression received the highest ratings of blame and perceived viciousness. This coincides with past research showing that Black defendants are often perceived as more violent, dangerous, and threatening, which can heighten perceptions of fault and responsibility (Mastro, 2015; Skinner et al., 2020). The primarily Latinx jurors may be displaying an out-group bias toward both White and Black defendants, especially in this situation where mental illness serves as a "nonracial" justification for differential treatment (Bradbury & Williams, 2013). The harsher judgements towards White and Black defendants in the current study suggest that Latinx jurors perceive both groups as out-groups, responding to them with similar patterns of aversive bias and making more favorable collective determinations towards Latinx defendants. This shared pattern reinforces the idea that aversive bias does not operate solely within a White–Black racial divide but can emerge in more nuanced ways depending on group dynamics, social context, and group membership. These outcomes also highlight the persistence of mental illness stigma that still operate in the courtroom and the leniency effect that tends to favor in-group members.

Consistent with Hypothesis Four, mock jurors rated Black and White defendants diagnosed with depression as less ethical and colder than Latino defendants or those diagnosed with schizophrenia. Significant main effects were found for both defendant race and mental illness diagnosis, further supporting that these defendants were also viewed as less trustworthy, less ethical, colder, and more aggressive overall. In line with the in-group/out-group bias observed across the previous dependent measures, White defendants—regardless of mental illness diagnosis—were rated as the least ethical, the least warm, and the most aggressive overall. These trait judgements reveal how racialized perceptions can subtly shape negative character evaluations. An explanation for these findings may be that mock juror’s evaluations reflect broader societal beliefs that depression is linked to moral weakness, impulsivity, or social withdrawal (Stuart, 2006). Racial stereotypes that equate Black men with danger or White men with entitlement may contribute to harsher character judgements. This intersection is in line with the “double stigma” hypothesis (Plummer et al., 2023), which argues that individuals with multiple marginalized identities (e.g., race and mental illness) experience exacerbated forms of bias that lead to negative trait attributions and further social exclusion.

Implications of Research

The results of this study suggest that jurors’ perceptions are heavily influenced by the intersection of race and mental illness diagnosis. Although such biases may not appear in overt sentencing or verdict outcomes, they were most evident in more subtle judgements of a defendants’ responsibility, intentionality, and other personal characteristics. Jurors did not openly express discrimination or prejudice but demonstrated bias through patterns of decision-making that were more punitive towards Black and White defendants with depression. This pattern aligns with the theory of *aversive racism*, which posits that bias towards minorities surfaces in ambiguous or subjective evaluations and operates at a covert level, allowing jurors to rationalize their unfair judgments through race-neutral explanations (Dovidio & Gaertner, 2004; Reynolds et al., 2022). Additionally, due to the limited number of studies examining specifically Hispanic jurors, the results of the present study should

be viewed as exploratory rather than conclusive. Addressing these dynamics is crucial for further exploration into juror decision-making bias and the demographics of defendants, victims, and jurors.

Taken together, these findings have important implications for understanding juror decision-making. They provide evidence that evaluations of defendants are shaped by more than just concrete facts of a case, in that, extra-legal factors play a role, particularly in shaping perceptions of culpability and personal trait assessments of the defendant. This is especially concerning for minorities, who already face disproportionate barriers in this historically oppressive institution (Bowdler & Harris, 2022; Harris & Feldmeyer, 2009). Jurors are able to attribute their punitive decisions to perceptions of individual responsibility rather than race. If these biased perceptions continue to prevail in our justice system, more stigma will be perpetuated against marginalized groups, reinforcing the negative cycles of disadvantage and undermining the integrity of a system that is meant to ensure fairness and justice for all.

In addition, the findings underscore the need for increased awareness and training within the legal system. Judges, jurors, and attorneys should be given more instruction on how subtle forms of prejudice or bias may operate during deliberations. Education programs on implicit biases can stress how mental illness stigma, psychiatric diagnoses, and racial stereotypes interact to influence perceptions of culpability and dangerousness. Another approach may involve including race-salient messages in court room procedures, as demonstrated in Gamblin and Kehn (2021). For example, before deliberations, attorneys might provide a brief reminder of how implicit biases unconsciously shape perceptions of evidence and credibility, thereby encouraging jurors to make decisions based solely on the facts presented. Similarly, interventions that remind jurors to actively monitor their judgments could include self-reflection checklists or breaks during deliberation in which jurors are asked to reflect on any strong emotional reactions or discomfort towards certain defendants and consider the underlying reasons for those responses. By making both race and mental illness stigma more salient in decision-making

contexts, and instructing jurors to these potential influences, it may be possible to reduce the extent to which these biases operate outside of conscious awareness (Leippe et al., 2023).

Limitations and Future Directions

There are several limitations that should be noted for the present study. First, we did not examine gender differences of either defendants or jurors. Past research has demonstrated differences between men and women in reactions to expert testimony involving defendants' mental health information, in that female jurors were likely to judge defendants more severely when described as "high-risk psychopaths" compared to defendants described simply as "high-risk" (Guy & Edens, 2003). Women mock jurors have also shown higher levels of empathy, endorsed more negative perceptions of defendant, and rendered more guilty verdicts when the victim is perceived as particularly vulnerable (Bottoms et al., 2011). The absence of gender as a variable limits the generalizability of the current results and future research should examine how both juror and defendant gender may interact with extra-legal factors to influence judgments.

Second, the participant sample consisted mostly of young college students, with a majority identifying as Latinx. While this provides valuable insight into how one demographic group may approach juror decision-making, it does not reflect the diversity of age, educational background, or racial/ethnic composition found in actual juror pools, limiting the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, the predominance of Latinx participants may have also limited the extent to which effects related to White jurors' aversive racism could be detected. Instead, our findings found a bias towards Black and White defendants, highlighting the importance of considering the cultural context of the mock jurors themselves. Latinx participants represent a group that has been historically underrepresented in juror decision-making research (Espinoza, 2010). The pattern we see in this study of harsher evaluations for both Black and White defendants may suggest an out-group effect, that reflects Latinx jurors' attempts to distance themselves from the historically dominant (White) and highly stigmatized (Black) groups within the U.S. racial hierarchy.

Finally, the artificial setting of a mock trial and the lack of real-world consequences limits the applicability and validity of the results. In actual trials, jurors experience different pressures, deliberation processes, and accountability for their decisions, which may alter how biases are expressed. A wide range of additional factors, such as personal experiences, cultural background, prior experiences in the legal system, and individual attitudes—may further shape judgments in ways that are not reflected in a mock trial setting. Future research should seek to replicate these findings with a larger and more diverse sample of participants to enhance generalizability. It would be valuable to ascertain whether similar patterns emerge across different types of crimes, varying levels of severity, and different defendant genders. Additionally, incorporating implicit bias measures and psychophysiological measures (e.g., eye-tracking) could offer deeper insight into the cognitive and affective mechanisms underlying aversive racism in juror decision-making.

Given that the present study was conducted at a minority-serving, liberal college with a primarily female sample, future work should also consider how demographic and ideological factors—such as political affiliation and educational background—may impact juror bias. Because aversive racism theory provides an explanation for bias among people who endorse egalitarian values, it is possible that our participants' liberal views skewed how patterns of bias are expressed. Furthermore, future studies should examine how jurors understand and interpret the severity of mental illness diagnoses, as misconceptions about conditions like depression and schizophrenia may hinder accurate assessments of defendant culpability and fairness in verdict decisions.

In conclusion, despite the limitations of our modest sample size and majority Latinx sample, the current findings demonstrate a need for individuals in the United States legal system to be educated to extra-legal influences on juror decisions. The results provide support that mock jurors' perceptions of defendants are influenced by the intersection of race and mental illness—consistent with the theory of aversive racism. This study contributes to the growing body of research exploring how stigmatizing and racialized perceptions of minority defendants with mental illness cause differential evaluations and

judgements in the courtroom. Judges and lawyers, as well as legislators at the local, state, and federal levels need to be aware of the potential impact of these biases on juror decisions. Disseminating the results to those within the legal system will be a crucial step toward promoting fairness and advancing social justice.

APPENDIX A

TABLES

Table 1. Chi-square Analyses of Interactive Effects of Defendant Race and Mental Illness Diagnosis (MID) for Verdict

Defendant Race and MID	Jury Verdict			Total
	Not Guilty	NGBRI	Guilty	
Black Def. Depression	1	13	17*	31
Black Def. Schizophrenia	3	16	14	33
Black Def. No Diagnosis	0	22	10	32
Latino Def. Depression	3	15	17	35
Latino Def. Schizophrenia	1	21	10	32
Latino Def. No Diagnosis	2	23	9	34
White Def. Depression	0	13	21*	34
White Def. Schizophrenia	0	22	11	33
White Def. No Diagnosis	1	18	10	29
Total	11	163	119	293

* $p < .05$

Table 2. Chi-square Analyses of Defendant Mental Illness Diagnosis (MID) for Verdict

Defendant MID	Jury Verdict			Total
	Not Guilty	NGBRI	Guilty	
Defendant Diagnosed w/ Depression	4	41	55*	100
Defendant Diagnosed w/ Schizophrenia	4	59	36	99
Defendant w/ No Diagnosis	3	28	63	94
Total	11	128	154	293

* $p < .005$

Table 3. Culpability for Mental Illness X Defendant Race ($N = 293$)

Defendant Race and MID	Culpability		
	Guilt	Blame	Viciousness
BD/Dep.	6.16*	6.71*	6.39*
LD/Dep.	5.00	5.29	5.43
WD/Dep.	6.44*	6.53*	5.47
BD/Schiz.	4.61	5.03	4.76
LD/Schiz.	4.91	4.88	4.84
WD/Schiz.	5.21	5.67	5.58
BD/No Diag.	5.19	5.16	5.06
LD/No Diag.	4.88	4.91	4.45
WD/No Diag.	5.00	5.28	5.34

* $p < .001$

Table 4. Culpability for Defendant Race ($N = 293$)

Defendant Race	Culpability					
	Guilt	Responsibility	Confidence	Future Crime	Belief	Blame
Black Def.	5.30	5.40	5.52	4.02	3.57	5.61
Latino Def.	4.90*	4.78*	4.93*	3.78*	3.84*	5.00*
White Def.	5.58	5.66	5.80	4.56	3.30	5.85

* $p < .001$

Table 5. Culpability for Mental Illness Diagnosis ($N = 293$)

MID	Culpability					
	Guilt	Responsibility	Confidence	Future Crime	Belief	Blame
Depression	5.85	5.94*	5.91*	4.32	3.57	6.15*
Schizophrenia	4.88*	5.00	5.06	3.87*	3.45*	5.16
No Diagnosis	5.02	4.84	5.24	4.16	3.71	5.11

* $p < .001$

Table 6. Trait Ratings for Mental Illness X Defendant Race ($N = 293$)

Defendant Race and MID	Trait Ratings	
	Ethical	Cold/Warm
BD/Dep.	2.26*	2.19*
LD/Dep.	3.56	3.68
WD/Dep.	1.88*	1.68*
BD/Schiz.	3.84	3.88
LD/Schiz.	4.09	4.12
WD/Schiz.	3.39	3.70
BD/No Diag.	4.22	4.28
LD/No Diag.	4.09	4.58
WD/No Diag.	3.93	3.50

* $p < .001$

Table 7. Trait Ratings for Defendant Race ($N = 293$)

Defendant Race	Trait Ratings			
	Trust	Ethicalness	Cold/Warm	Aggressiveness
Black Def.	3.26	3.47	3.48	6.83
Latino Def.	4.00*	3.88*	4.09*	6.27*
White Def.	3.51	3.04	2.95	7.28

* $p < .001$

Table 8. Trait Ratings for Defendant Mental Illness Diagnosis (MID) ($N = 293$)

MID	Trait Ratings			
	Trust	Ethicalness	Cold/Warm	Aggressiveness
Depression	3.35*	2.56*	2.51*	7.43*
Schizophrenia	3.52	3.79	3.91	6.59
No Diagnosis	3.94	4.11	4.17	6.31

* $p < .001$

APPENDIX B

INFORMED CONSENT

Informed Consent - Criminal Court Trial
(CSUF-IRB – Approval # HSR-18-19-201)

You must be 18 years of age or older to participate in this study. The purpose of this research project is to examine how jurors make decisions regarding criminal court trials. For this project you will be asked to act as a juror, read through a criminal court trial, and render a verdict in the case. In addition, you will be asked to answer various questions regarding the case and the parties involved. Lastly, there will be a short survey after you have finished answering all trial questions. The survey asks general questions about various social issues. Both parts of the study will take a total of approximately 45 minutes to complete.

All data will be maintained in a locked facility to which only the Principal Investigator has access. In addition, after giving your consent, the consent form and the answers you provide for the trial and survey questions will be separated to maintain complete anonymity to the fullest extent allowed by law. However, if you choose to withdraw at any time all of your data will be removed from the study.

The foreseeable risks or ill effects from participating in this study are minimal. You may feel uneasy rendering a verdict in the court case and answering some of the questions at the end of the trial transcript. However, you are free to stop the study at any time without penalty. There is a small possibility that answering some of the questions on the questionnaires may evoke some feelings of anxiety. You may end this study at any time should any feelings of anxiety arise.

There are three benefits to this study. First, you will be contributing to the scientific understanding of how jurors make informed decisions regarding court cases. Second, you may gain insight into how criminal court proceedings work in the United States legal system. Third, you are free to continue to maintain contact with the principal investigator to gain any more knowledge about the topic of psychology and law that you wish.

Your participation in this study is completely voluntary and you are free to withdraw from the study at any time for any reason without penalty or prejudice from the investigator. Please feel free to ask any questions of the investigator before signing the Informed Consent form and beginning the study, and at any time during the study. The Principal Investigator's contact information is as follows: Russ Espinoza, Ph. D., Department of Psychology, H-830M, California State University, Fullerton, Fullerton, CA 92831, [REDACTED], [REDACTED], [REDACTED] [@fullerton.edu](mailto:[REDACTED]@fullerton.edu).

For one's rights as a research subject, the following person may be contacted: Coordinator of Research Compliance, Office of Research and Development, California State University, Fullerton, CA, (657) 278-7640.

I, _____, agree to participate in this research project entitled, "Criminal Court Trial." I have had the study explained to me and my questions have been answered to my satisfaction. I have read the description of this project and give my consent to participate. If you consent to participate in this research please click the following link.

Participant Signature

Russ Espinoza, Ph. D.
Department of Psychology, H-725H
California State University, Fullerton
Fullerton, CA 92831

Phone: [REDACTED]
Email: [REDACTED] [@fullerton.edu](mailto:[REDACTED]@fullerton.edu)

APPENDIX C**TRIAL TRANSCRIPT**

IN THE COURT OF THE SIXTH JUDICIAL CIRCUIT IN AND FOR LOS ANGELES COUNTY,
STATE OF CALIFORNIA

CRIMINAL DIVISION

Case No. WD-WVSc2022
INDICTMENT

STATE OF CALIFORNIA

vs.

MICHAEL HENDERSON,

Defendant

Age 27

Sex Male

Race White

The grand jury in and for the county of Los Angeles, State of California, upon their oath and in the name and by the authority of the State of California, does hereby charge the following offense under the Criminal Code of the State of California:

That on September 1, 2017, at and within Los Angeles of Los Angeles in the State of California, MICHAEL HENDERSON committed the crime of

MULTIPLE MURDERS

IN VIOLATION OF SECTION 18-3-102 OF THE California Criminal Code of 1984, as amended, in that he after deliberation and with the intent to MURDER, had willfully shot and murdered MS. REBECCA MILLER (White female, age 26), and her two cousins, ROBERT TOMKINS (White male, age 28) and ASHLEY TOMKINS (White female, age 24), to death on the date of August 31, 2017.

Contrary to the form of the Statute and against the peace and dignity of the People of the State of California.

A TRUE BILL:

Foreperson of the Grand Jury

VICTIMS

REBECCA MILLER
(White female, age 26)

ROBERT TOMKINS
(White male, age 28)

ASHLEY TOMKINS
(White female, age 24)

CASE SUMMARY

On the morning of September 1, 2017, the ex-girlfriend's mother, DARLA MILLER, went to the apartment of her daughter because she could not reach her by telephone. She entered her daughter's apartment and noticed that the deadbolt was not locked. She found her daughter and her daughter's two cousins, who are brother and sister, in the main bedroom, lying in pools of blood. The daughter was slumped on the ground at the foot of the bed and the male cousin was slumped on the bed in a pool of blood, while his sister was on the right side of the bed lying on the floor in a pool of blood.

The coroner's report stated that the victims, REBECCA MILLER, (White female, age 26), ROBERT TOMKINS (White male, age 28), and ASHLEY TOMKINS (White female, age 24) were each shot between 7 and 15 times by an assault type rifle, and that they died of these wounds. Based on toxicology reports on the temperature of the victim's livers, the time of death for all three victims was estimated at approximately 9pm on August 31, 2017.

Police investigation revealed a stormy relationship between the adult victim and her former boyfriend by testimony of several of the victim's friends and the victim's mother. No police reports had ever been filed against the defendant by the adult victim, and based on the testimony of the victim's friends and mother, no known physical violence had ever occurred. However, the friends of the ex-girlfriend victim and the mother of the victim each stated that the defendant suffered from mental illness.

The State's evidence for arrest was based on fingerprints found at the scene, an eyewitness, TOM CUNNINGHAM, who stated he saw the defendant enter the victim's home around the date and time the murder occurred, carrying an oblong object, and from the victim's friends and mother, DARLA MILLER, who stated in a police interview that the relationship between the victim and the defendant was sometimes volatile, but no physical abuse had occurred to her knowledge. The mother goes on to state that her daughter had recently broken off the 2 and one-half year relationship with the defendant and that since the breakup her daughter had received harassing and threatening phone messages and emails.

The District Attorney of Los Angeles has charged MICHAEL HENDERSON with the murder of REBECCA MILLER, ROBERT TOMKINS and ASHLEY TOMKINS after the Los Angeles police investigation unit presented the gathered evidence to the District Attorney's Office. A warrant for MICHAEL HENDERSON'S arrest was issued by the Los Angeles courthouse and MICHAEL HENDERSON was arrested at his place of employment without incident. At the defendant's apartment an AK47 assault rifle, with automatic cartridges was found that was later determined to be the weapon used in the murders.

Defendant Background

The defendant, MICHAEL HENDERSON, is a 27-year-old White male who lives in a one-bedroom apartment in the city of Burbank in Los Angeles County. He has no other prior arrests or convictions. He grew up in Los Angeles and has a high school diploma from Burbank High School and has attended two years at Los Angeles Valley Community College but has no advanced degree. He currently works as a machine operator at Color Media Graphics Design Company.

The defendant has a long history of mental illness and has been diagnosed with schizophrenia since he turned 19 years of age. He has been homeless from time to time when he is not on his medication. He is being counseled by a licensed psychotherapist and sees a psychiatrist for medication.

Defendant Plea

The defendant is represented by defense attorney Harold Sullivan, a prominent attorney in Los Angeles. The defendant, MICHAEL HENDERSON, by suggestion of his counsel, Harold Sullivan, has entered a plea of Not Guilty by Reason of Insanity.

SUMMARY CASE FOR THE PROSECUTION

The case for the Prosecution was based on the testimony of the following parties:

Police Investigator James Smith: Lead Crime Scene Investigator who arrested Mr. Henderson

Darla Miller: Mother of victim

Tom Cunningham: Witnessed the defendant go into the apartment building at approximately the date and time of the murder

Jennifer Banks: Friend of victim

Terry Yakiyama: Forensics Investigating Technician

District attorney for the Prosecution, John Thompson, offers the following testimonial evidence:

Investigator James Smith testified that he was called to the crime scene at approximately 10am on September 1, 2017. At the crime scene he gathered information regarding possible suspects from interviewing the ex-girlfriend victim's mother. Investigator Smith states that it did not appear to be a break-in but the victim's purse was missing. There were no visible signs of a struggle other than the bullet holes around the master bedroom. There were finger prints of the defendant found intermittently throughout the apartment. Investigator Smith interviewed the eyewitness, TOM CUNNINGHAM, who stated he was sitting on the entrance steps having a beer on the night in question when he saw the defendant enter the apartment building carrying an oblong object. The witness then stated he went into his apartment and heard nothing else the rest of the evening but that he had the TV on loudly. Investigator Smith also interviewed the victim's mother who stated that the relationship between the victim and the defendant was often volatile and that the victim had recently ended the relationship because of the defendant's mental condition. After gathering this evidence, testimony, and information an arrest warrant was requested by the District Attorney's office and granted by Judge, QUENTIN

THOMAS, of the Los Angeles Criminal Court. The defendant was apprehended at his place of employment without incident.

Darla Miller testified that she went to her daughter's apartment on September 1, 2017 because her daughter missed a dinner appointment the night before and she could not reach her daughter by phone. Upon entering her daughter's apartment she noticed the door was closed but not locked. She called out for her daughter and her grandchildren and went into her daughter's bedroom where she found the victims on the bed and on the ground at the foot of the bed in pools of blood. She said she immediately started screaming and crying and called the police. She also testifies that during the police questioning she revealed that her daughter had recently broken up with her long-time boyfriend and that the boyfriend had started harassing her daughter with threatening phone calls and emails and seemed to be suffering from paranoid delusional behavior. She goes on to state that during the relationship that her daughter never mentioned being physically abused but that the victim and defendant had argued often but she witnessed several times bizarre behavior and signs of schizophrenia from the defendant. She was also aware that the defendant was taking medication for the mental disorder of schizophrenia.

Tom Cunningham testified that on the night of August 31, 2017 he was sitting on the entrance steps to the Riverview Gardens apartment complex, where the victim's body was found. He said he had been sitting on the apartment entrance steps drinking a 'couple of beers' when he saw the defendant, wearing a dark sweatshirt and Levis, and carrying an oblong object, enter the complex at about 8pm. He states he was on the steps for an additional 30 minutes or so and then went back into his apartment. He states he didn't hear or see anything else that night that was suspicious.

Jennifer Banks, a friend of the victim, stated that she had known the victim for years and that she knew the defendant as well. She states her and her boyfriend often double-dated with the victim and the defendant and never saw any physical abuse between the victim and defendant but knew that the defendant had "mental problems". She states after the victim broke off the relationship that Rebecca confided in her that the defendant was harassing her and leaving threatening, paranoid messages on her phone answering machine and that she felt scared that he was off of his medication.

Terry Yakiyama, the forensics lab technician, testified that REBECCA MILLER, (White female, age 26), ROBERT TOMKINS (White male, age 28), and ASHLEY TOMKINS (White female, age 24) each died of multiple gunshot wounds from the AK47 assault rifle registered to the defendant, MICHAEL HENDERSON. He states that REBECCA MILLER was shot 12 times in the head, torso, and right arm. ROBERT TOMKINS was shot 15 times in the torso and arms, and that ASHLEY TOMKINS was shot 7 times in the head and torso. He goes on to state that the bedroom had 37 other bullet holes and bullets found at the scene, and in the walls and furniture of the bedroom.

SUMMARY OF CASE FOR THE DEFENSE

The case for the Defense was based on the testimony of the following parties:

MICHAEL HENDERSON:	Defendant, currently employed at Color Media Graphics
Patrick Moore:	Friend and neighbor of defendant
Sally Jenkins:	Counselor of defendant
Terry Howard:	Social Worker to defendant

OPENING ARGUMENTS FOR THE DEFENSE

Defense attorney, Harold Sullivan, began his opening remarks by stating that the defendant suffers from a severe form of paranoid, delusional schizophrenia and that he is not responsible for his actions. According to the M'Naghten Rule, which states that in order for a defendant to be found guilty it must be demonstrated that he 1) was not suffering from a defect of reason, a "disease of the mind", 2) did not "know" the nature and quality of act he/she was doing, and 3) as a result, did not know what he/she was doing was wrong. He goes on to state that because the defendant, Michael Henderson, was diagnosed with severe paranoid delusional schizophrenia, he could not have known that what he was doing was wrong. In addition, he goes on to state that his client, Michael Henderson, does not remember most of the evening in question.

MICHAEL HENDERSON testified that on the night in question he had met with the victim and that they had discussed their breakup but that it was amicable and that he does not remember anything else of the evening. He said he was never threatening or harassing to the victims and that he was merely upset that the relationship was over but he went on to start mumbling incoherently. He testified that though the breakup was not pleasant he still loved the victim and would never hurt her, but again, went on to start mumbling incoherently. He goes on to state that there has never had a history of violence with the victims and that he has no prior history of arrests. He also states that he has been switching medications to treat his schizophrenia but that he feels better now and he just does not remember anything after the amicable conversation with the victims.

Patrick Moore testified that on the night in question Mr. Moore was working on his car in his driveway and saw the defendant leave his house about 7:30 p.m. on August 31, 2017, but that he didn't take any particular notice to this as most of this as Mr. Henderson was always coming and going. He also testified that the defendant returned approximately an hour or so later and did not appear agitated in anyway, and that he waved to the defendant but the defendant did not wave back. He goes on to state that he has seen, on occasion, Mr. Henderson talking to himself and "acting bizarre" at times but he has not seen him be violent.

Sally Jenkins testified that she had been counseling the defendant, Michael Henderson, for about 16 months. She states that Mr. Henderson is a good person and that he had been seeing a regular psychiatrist on and off for the past two years to adjust his medications. She goes on to state that she had seen him both on, and off, of his medication. She states when he is on his medication, which he had been while he was seeing her, he could not have committed this act.

Terry Howard, the defendant's social worker since the defendant was 11 years old, testified that the defendant, Michael Henderson, has a history of being physically abused by his father during his childhood. He has been in and out of social agencies since the first allegations of abuse, but has succeeded in overcoming these earlier childhood traumas and has adjusted well to life. He states that the defendant, Mr. Henderson, can be quite a different person when he is not taking his meds, but doesn't believe that Mr. Henderson is capable of such an act.

CLOSING ARGUMENTS FOR THE PROSECUTION

The district attorney, John Thompson, for the prosecution summarized his case against MICHAEL HENDERSON by arguing that the evidence and testimony against the defendant was overwhelming. That there is no physical evidence against any other person for this murder and that his fingerprints were found around the apartment. He goes on to state that the defendant had motive and was identified to be in the apartment at the approximate time of the murder. He states that the defendant was harassing the victim and leaving threatening phone messages after the breakup and that he was aware that what he was doing was wrong and that mental illness is not to blame for these murders. "The defendant stalked the victim and her children, went into the apartment with the intent to kill and shot up the bedroom with almost 100 rounds of ammunition. He goes on to state that one of the first arriving officers described the scene as a 'war zone'. All of this evidence clearly points out that the defendant, MICHAEL HENDERSON, is guilty of Murder, as he willfully killed the victims, REBECCA MILLER, and her two cousins ROBERT TOMKINS and ASHLEY TOMKINS," district attorney, John Thompson, stated.

CLOSING ARGUMENTS FOR THE DEFENSE

The defense attorney, Harold Sullivan, summarized his defense of MICHAEL HENDERSON by stating that the prosecution did not prove without a shadow of a doubt that the defendant committed the crime. First, the

investigation never bothered to look for any other suspects. He goes on to state that the defendant's fingerprints were around the apartment because he was over there quite often during their relationship. He goes on to state that the neighbor noticed no difference in demeanor when he returned home, and saw no noticeable traces of blood on the defendant. He also points out to the defendant's counselor and the court appointed psychiatrist which went on to describe all of Michael Henderson's good qualities and that he suffers from schizophrenia and was having his medication adjusted at the time the murders took place. In addition, he goes on to state the defendant does not remember the night in question and that if he did do these crimes that he is not responsible for them because he did not understand the consequences of his behavior because of his mental illness. He goes on to state that if they find the defendant committed the crimes he should be remanded to a mental health hospital to seek treatment for his mental disorder. "All of this evidence adds up to one thing: there is plenty of reasonable doubt about if the defendant was in a right state of mind to commit these crimes and know what he was doing at the time of the crimes was wrong," defense attorney Harold Sullivan stated.

GENERAL JUROR INSTRUCTIONS

The State of California has charged the defendant, MICHAEL HENDERSON, with Murder. To prove that charge, it must be shown that:

- (a) the defendant willfully killed the victims, and
- (b) the defendant was acting on his own accord and not under duress,
- (c) the defendant was not suffering from a defect of reason, a "disease of the mind"
- (d) the defendant knew the nature and quality of the act he/she was doing and as a result, understood that what he/she was doing was wrong.

If you find from your consideration of all the evidence presented that each of the above four propositions has not been proved, then you should find the defendant Not Guilty or Not Guilty By Reason Of Insanity.

APPENDIX D

JUROR EVALUATIONS

JUROR VERDICT AND SENTENCE FORM

IN THE CIRCUIT COURT OF

LOS ANGELES COUNTY, CALIFORNIA

Case No. WD-WVSc2022

THE PEOPLE OF THE STATE OF CALIFORNIA)	
)	
vs.)	
)	JURY VERDICT
MICHAEL HENDERSON)	
Defendant)	

I, acting as a juror in the case of the State of California vs. MICHAEL HENDERSON, return the following verdict:

NOT GUILTY _____

NOT GUILTY BY REASON OF INSANITY _____

GUILTY _____

If you found the defendant, MICHAEL HENDERSON, guilty of Murder, the state provides for three sentencing options. Please indicate which of the three options is appropriate. (If you indicated that the defendant was not guilty on the juror verdict form, please skip the sentencing question and complete the remaining forms).

Sentence if found NOT GUILTY BY REASON OF INSANITY

_____ Released under the supervision of psychiatrist Sally Jenkins

_____ Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff

_____ Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff, whereby the defendant will serve 20 years for the murders

Sentence if found GUILTY

_____ Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 20 years and time for good behavior

_____ Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 30 years and time for good behavior

_____ Life in prison without the possibility of parole

JUROR OPINION FORM

Please answer the following questions about the case description that you have just read. If you wish, you may refer to the case description as an aid to answering the questions. Either circle the appropriate point on the scales below or fill in the blank.

1. How guilty do you think the defendant actually is?

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____

Not guilty
at all

Completely
guilty

2. How long of a sentence do you think the defendant should actually receive?

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____

Nothing/Innocent

Death

3. In your opinion, how responsible is MICHAEL HENDERSON for committing this crime?

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____

Not at all
responsible

Totally
responsible

4. How confident are you that you have made a correct guilt decision?

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____

Not confident
at all

Extremely
confident

5. How likely is it that the defendant will commit this crime again in the future?

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____

Not at all
Likely

Totally
Likely

6. How much do you believe the defendant's version of the crime?

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____

Not at all

Completely

7. How likely is it that you would find yourself in a similar situation as the defendant?

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____

Not at all
Likely

Highly
Likely

8. How much of the blame for the incident should the defendant receive?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- None of it All of it
9. How likely is it that the defendant committed this same crime in the past?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- Not at all likely Extremely Likely
10. How much did the situation influence the defendant's behavior?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- Not at all Completely
11. To what degree do you think the defendant intentionally meant to kill the victims?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- No Intention Full Intention
12. To what degree do you think the defendant lied to the police?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- Not at all Extremely
- Likely Likely
13. How much did the viciousness of the attacks impact your decision?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- Not at all Completely
14. Do you believe the defendant's mental illness is the main reason for the murder?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- Not at all Completely
15. How much did the defendant's mental illness influence your decision?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- Not at all Completely
16. Do you believe the defendant is mentally ill, and therefore not responsible for his actions?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- Not at all Completely
17. Do you believe the defendant is mentally ill, and therefore did not know right from wrong?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- Not at all Completely
18. How much experience do you have knowing someone with schizophrenia?
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
- None A great deal of experience

(2) What was the defendant's racial or ethnic background?

(3) What was the charge against the defendant?

(4) What was the defendant's mental illness?

JUROR BACKGROUND FORM

The following questions are intended to provide some basic demographic information about the jurors. Your answers to the following questions will be combined with the answers of many other jurors, and your answers will remain completely anonymous.

Participant Demographic Information

1. How many people live in and shared the same household you grew up in? (Circle one)

2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 or more

2. What was the combined yearly income of both your parents, or yourself if you are living independently? If you don't know for sure, estimate. (Circle one)

\$20,000 or less = _____ \$20,000 – 50,000 = _____ \$50,001 – 80,000 = _____

\$80,001 – 125,000 = _____ \$125,001 or more = _____

3. What was the last grade finished or degree earned by your parents in school? (Circle one for your father and one for your mother)

3a. Father –

3b. Mother –

_____ Up to grade 8

_____ Some high school (grades 9-12)

_____ High school diploma / GED

_____ Some college

_____ College degree

_____ Some post-graduate work

_____ Post-graduate degree

_____ Up to grade 8

_____ Some high school (grades 9-12)

_____ High school diploma / GED

_____ Some college

_____ College degree

_____ Some post-graduate work

_____ Post-graduate degree

4. Which is your gender? Male _____ Female _____

5. What is your age? _____

6. What is your Race/Nationality/Ethnicity:

White-European-American _____

African-American _____

Hispanic _____

Native-American _____

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